

Triterpenoids from the orchid *Eria acervata*

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Abstract : Acervatol and acervatone, two new triterpenoids, were isolated from the orchid *Eria acervata*. The structures of acervatol and acervatone were established as 24,24-dimethyl-lanosta-9(11)-en-3 β -ol (**2a**) and 24,24-dimethyl-lanosta-9(11)-en-3-one (**2c**), respectively, from spectral and chemical evidence. These triterpenoids are of considerable biogenetic importance providing circumstantial evidence for the modification of the C-17 side chain of the lanostane skeleton through methionine-induced C-methylation involving allylic rearrangement.

Keywords : Acervatol, acervatone, triterpenoids, orchidaceae, *Eria acervata*.

We reported earlier the isolation of a fairly large number of compounds from a series of Indian orchids. These compounds encompass a wide variety of stilbenoids¹ and a few other polyphenolics², several triterpenoids^{3,4}, steroids of biogenetic importance⁵ and some simple aromatic compounds⁶. As part of this general programme of research, we have chemically investigated yet another Indian orchid *Eria acervata*. This has resulted in the isolation of two new triterpenoids, designated acervatol and acervatone, besides the known stilbenoids coelonin⁷ (**1a**), flavanthrinin⁸ (**1b**), nudol⁹ (**1c**) and confusarin¹⁰ (**2d**). While the known compounds were characterized by direct comparison with their respective authentic samples, the structures of acervatol and acervatone were established as 24,24-dimethyl-lanosta-9(11)-en-3 β -ol (**2a**) and 24,24-dimethyl-lanosta-9(11)-en-3-one (**2c**), respectively, from the following spectral and chemical evidence.

Results and discussion

Acervatol (**2a**), m.p. 190 °C, $[\alpha]_D + 73.15^\circ$ (CHCl₃), and acervatone (**2c**), m.p. 180 °C, $[\alpha]_D + 69.51^\circ$ (CHCl₃), analyzed for C₃₂H₅₆O and C₃₂H₅₄O, respectively, which were confirmed by their respective mass spectrometrically derived molecular weights 456 and 454.

The IR spectrum of both **2a** and **2c** showed bands which are characteristic of a trisubstituted olefinic double bond [**2a** : ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) 1637 and 806; **2c** : ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) 1645 and 769-794]. But while the spectrum of **2a** showed

a band at ν_{\max} 3393 cm⁻¹ for a hydroxyl group, that of **2c** is devoid of any such absorption, and, instead, exhibited an intense band at ν_{\max} 1705 cm⁻¹ for a six-membered cyclic keto carbonyl function. This would suggest that while **2c** contains a cyclohexanone moiety, **2a** is the corresponding secondary alcohol. The above contention was confirmed by the fact that **2c** on reduction with NaBH₄ in MeOH afforded **2a**. The presence of a hydroxyl function in **2a** was also confirmed by the formation of an acetyl derivative **2b**, C₃₄H₅₈O₂ ([M⁺] at *m/z* 498), m.p. 178-180 °C, on treatment with Ac₂O and pyridine.

The ¹H NMR spectrum of each of **2a**, **2b** and **2c** showed signals for ten methyl groups attached to sp³ carbon atoms [**2a** : δ 0.65, 0.74, 0.82, 0.99 and 1.05 (each 3H, s), 0.84 (6H, s), 0.79 (6H, d, *J* 6.67 Hz) and 0.87 (3H, d, *J* 6.27 Hz); **2b** : δ 0.65, 0.74, 0.86, 0.89 and 1.07 (each 3H, s), 0.84 (6H, s), 0.79 (6H, d, *J* 6.68 Hz) and 0.87 (3H, d, *J* 6.36 Hz); **2c** : δ 0.68 and 0.75 (each 3H, s), 0.79 (6H, d, *J* 6.53 Hz), 0.84 (9H, s), 0.87 (3H, d, *J* 6.35 Hz) and 1.07 (6H, s)] and a trisubstituted olefinic proton [**2a** : δ 5.22 (1H, ill-res. m); **2b** : δ 5.23 (1H, ill-res. m) and **2c** : δ 5.21 (1H, ill-res. m)]. The above ¹H NMR spectral data thus indicate the triterpenoid skeletal structure of **2a**, **2b** and **2c**, each possessing a trisubstituted olefinic double bond and two more methyl groups in addition to eight such functions in a normal tetracyclic triterpene of the lanostane type. The presence of a hydroxyl group attached to a cyclohexane ring in **2a** was

indicated by the appearance of a signal at δ 3.22 (1H, dd, J_1 11.60 Hz and J_2 4.31 Hz) for a hydroxymethine proton in the ^1H NMR spectrum of the compound. The corresponding signal for the acetoxymethine proton of **2b** appeared at δ 4.48 (1H, dd, J_1 11.64 Hz and J_2 4.34 Hz). The chemical shifts and the splitting patterns of the above protons of **2a** and **2b** are strikingly similar to those of the H-3 of **2d**⁴ and **2e**⁴, respectively, and indicate their axial nature coupling with an axial and an equatorial proton attached to one of the neighbouring carbon atoms, the other adjacent carbon atom being fully substituted. The hydroxyl group in **2a** and the acetoxyl function in **2b** must, therefore, be equatorially oriented. The ^1H NMR spectrum of **2c**, as expected, is devoid of the above signal, and, instead, showed a two-proton multiplet at δ 2.59–2.66 for a ketomethylene group.

The EI mass spectra of **2a** and **2c** showed intense peaks at m/z 313 and 311, respectively. These peaks were attributed to the ion-fragments **a** and **b** and were assumed to be formed by the loss of the C-17 side chain and two hydrogen atoms from the respective molecular ions of **2a** and **2c**. The appearance of these peaks in the mass spectra of **2a** and **2c** not only indicates the tetracyclic lanostane type of skeletal structure of the compounds, but also suggests the placement of the two additional C-methyls and the trisubstituted double bond in the C-17 side chain and the carbocyclic part, respectively, of both the compounds. These peaks which are also discernible in the mass spectra of **2d**⁴ and **2f**⁴, respectively, further indicate the placement of the hydroxyl functions in **2a** and the keto group in **2c** in the alicyclic part of their molecules.

The structures of **2a** and **2c** were finally confirmed by the ^{13}C NMR spectral data of the compounds and those of **2b** (Table 1). The degree of protonation of each carbon atom of the compounds were determined by DEPT experiment and in the case of **2a** from its HMQC and HMBC spectra. The presence of a trisubstituted double bond in all the three compounds were indicated by the appearance of two sp^2 carbon signals in each compound [**2a** : δ_{C} 114.9 and 148.4; **2b** : δ_{C} 115.2 and 148.2; **2c** : δ_{C} 116.4 and 147.1]. Again, the presence of a hydroxymethine carbon in **2a**, an acetoxymethine carbon in **2b** and a cyclic keto carbonyl function in **2c** was affirmed by the characteristic carbon resonances at δ_{C} 78.8, 80.9 and 216.6, respectively, exhibited by the spectra of the compounds. The assignments of the carbon chemical shifts of

2a, **2b** and **2c** in terms of a lanostane skeletal structure having two additional methyl groups at C-24, a 9,11-double bond in all the three compounds and their respective oxygen functions at C-3 were made by comparison of their δ_{C} values with those of the structurally similar compounds **2d**, **2e**, **2f**, **2g**, **2h** and related compounds¹¹. Thus, the virtually identical δ_{C} values of C-1–C-21 and C-28–C-30 of **2a** and **2d**⁴ and those of **2b** and **2e**⁴ affirmed the carbocyclic part and C-20 and C-21 of the C-17 side chain of the lanostane skeletal structure of **2a** and **2b**, both containing a 9,11-double bond and the former possessing a β -hydroxy function at C-3, while the latter having a β -acetoxyl group at the same position. Similarly, the essentially identical δ_{C} values of the above carbon atoms of **2c**, **2f**⁴, **2g**¹² and **2h**¹³ confirmed the identical structure of the carbocyclic part and the acyclic side chain containing C-20 and C-21 of all the four compounds having a keto group at C-3 and a 9,11-double bond in a lanostane basic skeletal structure. The placement of the trisubstituted double bond between C-7 and C-8 in **2c** and hence in **2a** was ruled out by the fact that this would have led to a considerable downfield shift of the olefinic methine carbon [*ca.* δ_{C} 121.0 (C-7)] as observed in 20(*R*),24(*E*)-3-oxo-9 β -lanosta-7,24-dien-26-oic acid¹⁴ [δ_{C} 148.8 (C-8) and 121.4 (C-7)].

The remaining six carbon resonances of each of **2a** (δ_{C} 14.1, 27.3, 28.1, 33.0, 35.1 and 43.0), **2b** (δ_{C} 14.1, 27.3, 28.2, 33.0, 35.2 and 43.2) and **2c** (δ_{C} 14.1, 27.3, 28.2, 33.0, 35.2 and 43.2) must, therefore, be attributed to their respective C-22–C-27 and the two additional methyl carbon atoms (C-31 and C-32). The virtually identical δ_{C} values of the above carbon atoms of **2a**, **2b** and **2c** implied that the acyclic side chain attached to C-20 of all these compounds must have the same structure. The above six carbon resonances of each of these compounds corresponded to two methylene carbons (**2a** : δ_{C} 28.1 and 35.1; **2b** and **2c** : δ_{C} 28.2 and 35.2), one non-protonated carbon at δ_{C} 33.0, one methine carbon (**2a** : δ_{C} 43.0; **2b** and **2c**; δ_{C} 43.2) and four methyl carbons, two resonating at δ_{C} 14.1 and the other two at δ_{C} 27.3. The HMQC spectrum of **2a** showed that the six-proton doublet at δ_{H} 0.79 (J 6.67 Hz) and the six-proton singlet at δ_{H} 0.84 corresponding to the above four methyl groups of the compound exhibited 1-bond correlations with its carbon resonances at δ_{C} 14.1 and 27.3, respectively. This would suggest that while the carbon resonance at δ_{C} 14.1 of each of

Table 1. ^{13}C NMR spectral data of **2a**, **2b**, **2c**, **2d**, **2e**, **2f**, **2g** and **2h**

C	Chemical shifts (δ ppm) ^a							
	2a	2b	2c	2d	2e	2f	2g	2h
1	36.0	35.9	36.7	36.1	35.8	36.7	36.7	36.7
2	27.7	24.2	34.7	27.8 ^a	24.1	35.0	34.9	34.9
3	78.8	80.9	216.6	78.9	80.8	217.1	217.2	217.2
4	39.3	38.0	47.0	39.3 ^b	38.0	47.0	46.9	46.9
5	52.4	52.7	53.5	52.5	52.6	53.5	53.4	53.4
6	21.3	21.2	22.6	21.3	21.0	22.6	22.5 [†]	22.5 ^{††}
7	28.0	28.0	27.7	28.1 ^a	27.9	27.7	27.7 [†]	27.7 ^{††}
8	41.7	41.6	41.9	41.8	41.6	41.9	41.8	41.8
9	148.4	148.2	147.1	148.5	148.1	147.1	147.0	147.0
10	39.0	39.3	39.0	39.0 ^b	39.2	39.0	39.0	39.0
11	114.9	115.2	116.4	114.9	115.2	116.3	116.7	116.7
12	37.1	37.2	37.3	37.2	37.2	37.2	37.1	37.1
13	44.2	44.3	44.3	44.3	44.3	44.3	44.2	44.2
14	46.9	47.0	47.6	47.0	47.0	47.6	47.7	47.7
15	33.8	33.9	33.9	33.9	33.9	33.0	33.9	33.9
16	28.0	28.2	28.0	27.9 ^a	27.9	27.9	27.0	27.9
17	51.1	50.9	51.1	50.9	50.9	50.9	50.8	50.7
18	14.3	14.4	14.4	14.3	14.4	14.4	14.4	14.4
19	22.2	22.2	21.7	22.2	22.2	22.0	21.8	21.8
20	36.1	36.0	36.1	36.1	36.0	36.1	36.0	36.6
21	18.4	18.6	18.4	18.4 ^c	18.4 ^a	18.4 ^a	18.6	18.5
22	28.1	28.2	28.2	35.1	35.1	34.8	33.9	30.7
23	35.1	35.2	35.2	31.2	31.3	31.3	31.4	37.3
24	33.0	33.0	33.0	156.8	156.6	156.7	41.6	38.7
25	43.0	43.2	43.2	33.8	33.8	33.8	150.1	152.3
26	14.1	14.1	14.1	21.9 ^d	21.9 ^b	21.7 ^b	109.4	109.3
27	14.1	14.1	14.1	21.8 ^d	21.8 ^b	21.8 ^b	20.2	19.4
28	18.2	18.4	18.2	18.3 ^c	18.3 ^a	18.3 ^a	18.4	18.4
29	28.14	28.1	25.7	28.2	28.1	25.7	25.6	25.6
30	15.5	16.5	21.9	15.5	16.7	22.0	22.0	22.0
31	27.3	27.3	27.3	105.9	106.0	106.0	18.0	27.2
32	27.3	27.3	27.3	-	-	-	-	27.5
OCOCH ₃	-	170.5	-	-	170.4	-	-	-
OCOCH ₃	-	21.5	-	-	21.2 ^b	-	-	-

^aSpectra were run in CDCl₃ and the chemical shifts were measured with $\delta_{(\text{TMS})} = \delta_{(\text{CDCl}_3)} + 76.9$ ppm.

^{a,b,c,d}Values are interchangeable in each column.

[†]Original assignments are interchanged.

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the above compounds may be assigned to their C-26 and C-27, that at δ_c 27.3 corresponds to the two additional methyl groups (C-31 and C-32) which, from biogenetic consideration, may be assumed to be located at C-24 reso-

nating at δ_c 33.0. The placement of the two additional methyl groups at C-24 in each of **2a**, **2b** and **2c** was also supported by the upfield shift (γ -effect) of a methylene carbon (**2a** : δ_c 28.1; **2b** and **2c** : δ_c 28.2) and the rela-

tively lowfield shift (β -effect) of another methylene carbon (**2a** : δ_c 35.1; **2b** and **2c** : δ_c 35.2) and the methine carbon (**2a** : δ_c 43.0; **2b** and **2c** : δ_c 43.2), which may, therefore, be assigned to C-22, C-23 and C-25, respectively, in each compound. The unusually high-field shift of C-26 and C-27 (δ_c 14.1) of the above compounds may presumably be due to severe gauche-butane interactions of the methyl groups associated with the above carbon atoms with those at C-24 (C-31 and C-32) and the methylene group (C-23) as shown in the three noneclipsed conformations of the C-17 side chain (Fig. 1) of these compounds.

The assignments of the chemical shifts of most of the carbon atoms of the C-17 side chain as well as those of the carbocyclic part of **2a** were finally confirmed by 1-

bond (HMQC) and 2- and 3-bond (HMBC) ^1H - ^{13}C correlation spectral analysis. The assignments of the corresponding carbon resonances of **2b** and **2c** were also affirmed by analogy with those of **2a**. Thus, H₃-26 and H₃-27 [δ_{H} 0.79 (6H, d, J 6.67 Hz)], which showed 1-bond correlation with the carbons at δ_c 14.1 (C-26 and C-27) exhibited a 2-bond correlation with the methine carbon at δ_c 43.0 (C-25) and a 3-bond correlation with the nonprotonated carbon at δ_c 33.0 (C-24). Again, H₃-31 and H₃-32 [δ_{H} 0.84 (6H, s)] which showed a 1-bond correlation with the carbons at δ_c 27.3 (C-31 and C-32) also displayed a 2-bond correlation with the carbon at δ_c 33.0 (C-24) and a 3-bond correlation with the carbon at δ_c 43.0 (C-25). The protons at δ_{H} 0.87 (3H, d, J 6.27 Hz) [H₃-21] which showed 1-bond correlation with the carbon at δ_c 18.4 (C-21) exhibited a 2-bond correlation with the methine carbon at δ_c 36.1 (C-20) and 3-bond correlations with the methine carbon at δ_c 51.1 (C-17) and the methylene carbon at δ_c 28.1 (C-22). H₃-18 (δ_{H} 0.65, 3H, s) exhibiting 1-bond correlation with the carbon at δ_c 14.3 (C-18), showed a 2-bond correlation with the nonprotonated carbon at δ_c 44.2 (C-13) and 3-bond correlations with the carbons at δ_c 51.1 (C-17), 46.9 (C-14) and 37.1 (C-12). Similarly the protons at δ_{H} 0.74 (3H, s) [H₃-28] which showed 1-bond correlation with the carbon at δ_c 18.2 (C-28) exhibited a 2-bond correlation with the nonprotonated carbon at δ_c 46.9 (C-14) and 3-bond correlations with the carbons at δ_c 44.2 (C-13), 33.8 (C-15) and 41.7 (C-8). The most readily identifiable olefinic proton at δ_{H} 5.22 (ill-res. m) [H-11] which exhibited 1-bond correlation with the lone protonated sp^2 carbon at δ_c 115.2 (C-11) showed a 2-bond correlation with the methylene carbon at δ_c 37.1 (C-12) and 3-bond correlations with the carbons at δ_c 44.2 (C-13), 41.7 (C-8) and 39.0 (C-10). The protons at δ_{H} 1.05 (3H, s) [H₃-19] exhibiting 1-bond correlation with the carbon at δ_c 22.2 (C-19) showed a 2-bond correlation with the carbon at δ_c 39.0 (C-10) and 3-bond correlations with the carbons at δ_c 36.0 (C-1), 52.4 (C-5) and 148.4 (C-9). Another readily identifiable proton is H-3 (δ_{H} 3.22, dd, J_1

Fig. 1. Three possible noneclipsed conformations of the C₁₇-side chain of **2a** and **2c**.

11.60 Hz and J_2 4.31 Hz) exhibiting 1-bond correlation with the hydroxymethine carbon at δ_c 78.8 (C-3) showed a 2-bond correlation with the nonprotonated carbon at δ_c 39.3 (C-4) and 3-bond correlations with the methyl carbons at δ_c 15.5 (C-30) and 28.14 (C-29) and the methylene carbon at δ_c 36.0 (C-1), H₃-29 (δ_H 0.99, 3H, s) and H₃-30 (δ_H 0.82, 3H, s) showed 1-bond correlations with the carbons at δ_c 28.14 (C-29) and 15.5 (C-30), respectively. H₃-29 and H₃-30 both showed a 2-bond correlation with the nonprotonated carbon at δ_c 39.3 (C-4) and 3-bond correlations with the carbons at δ_c 78.8 (C-3) and 52.4 (C-5). H₃-29 and H₃-30 also showed 3-bond correlations with the carbons at δ_c 15.5 (C-30) and 28.14 (C-29), respectively. The 2- and 3-bond ¹H-¹³C correlations exhibited by the HMBC spectrum of **2a** are shown on its structural diagram (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. 2- and 3-bond ¹H-¹³C correlations observed in the HMBC spectrum of **2a**.

Acervatol (**2a**) and acervatone (**2c**) are thus two new additions to the growing list of naturally occurring tetracyclic triterpenoids of the lanostane skeleton having two additional methyl groups at C-24. Biogenetically they are of considerable importance providing circumstantial evidence for the modification of the C-17 side chain of the lanostane skeleton presumably through methionine-induced C-methylation involving allylic rearrangement¹⁵.

Experimental

Melting points : uncorr. CC : silica gel (100–200 mesh). TLC : silica gel G. IR : KBr discs. ¹H and ¹³C NMR : 300 (500 MHz for **2a**) and 75 MHz (125 MHz for **2a**), respectively. NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃

and chemical shifts were expressed in δ (ppm). The HMQC and HMBC spectra of **2a** were recorded with J_{C-H} parameters set to 160 Hz and 7 Hz, respectively. MS : direct inlet system, 70 eV. All analytical samples were routinely dried over P₂O₅ for 24 h *in vacuo* and were tested for purity by TLC and MS. The petrol used had b.p. 60–80 °C. Anhydrous Na₂SO₄ was used for drying organic solvents.

Plant materials :

E. acervata Lindl. was collected from Kalimpong (Darjeeling, India) in October 2000. A Voucher specimen (Majumder s.n.) was deposited in the Herbarium of the Department of Botany, University of Calcutta (CUH).

Isolation of acervatol (**2a**) and acervatone (**2c**) :

Air-dried finely powdered whole plant of *E. acervata* (2 kg) was kept soaked in MeOH (5 l) for 3 weeks. The MeOH extract was concentrated to *ca.* 100 ml, diluted with H₂O (500 ml) and exhaustively extracted with Et₂O. The Et₂O extract was fractionated into acidic and nonacidic fractions with 2 M NaOH. The aqueous alkaline solution was acidified in the cold with conc. HCl and the liberated solids were extracted with Et₂O, washed with H₂O, dried and the solvent removed. The Et₂O extract containing the nonacidic constituents (left after NaOH treatment) was also washed with H₂O, dried and the solvent removed. The residues containing the acidic and nonacidic compounds were separately chromatographed.

(a) Chromatography of the acidic fraction obtained from *E. acervata* :

The petrol-EtOAc (15 : 1) afforded a mixture of **1a** and **1b**, which on rechromatography using the same solvent gave pure **1b** (0.08 g) as a glassy solid in the earlier fractions. The later fractions of the same eluate afforded pure **1a** (0.09 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 84 °C. Washing the column with petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) yielded a mixture of **1c** and **1d**. Repeated chromatography of the above mixture using the same eluent afforded pure **1c** (0.1 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 185 °C, in the earlier fractions. The later fractions in the above rechromatography gave **1d** (0.08 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc mixture, m.p. 185 °C.

(b) Chromatography of the nonacidic fraction obtained from *E. acervata* :

Elution of the column with light petroleum ether gave an uncharacterized oily mass. Further elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (50 : 1) afforded acervatone (**2c**) (0.40 g), crystallized from MeOH-CHCl₃ (9 : 1) mix-

ture, m.p. 180 °C (Found : C, 84.53; H, 11.94. C₃₂H₅₄O requires : C, 84.50; H, 11.98%); IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1705 (six-membered cyclic ketone), 1649 (nonconjugated C=C), 1462, 2952 and 669–800 (C–H stretching and C–H bending, respectively, of trisubstituted double bond), 1374, 1115 and 960; MS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 454 [M⁺] (39.5), 439 (73.8), 425 (4.3), 311 (10.3), 271 (5.4), 257 (9.1), 245 (9.1), 161 (3.8), 125 (16.5), 121 (7.5), 119 (6.4), 100 (7.5), 108 (7.5), 89 (11), 88 (10.5), 80 (9.5), 69 (12.8) and 54 (100).

Further elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (30 : 1) gave acervatol (**2a**) (0.20 g), crystallized from MeOH-CHCl₃ (9 : 1) mixture, m.p. 190 °C (Found : C, 84.18; H, 12.31. C₃₂H₅₆O requires : C, 84.13; H, 12.37%); IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3393 (OH), 1637 (nonconjugated C=C), 1460, 1372, 1264, 1096, 1039 and 2946 and 669–806 (C–H stretching and C–H bending, respectively, of trisubstituted double bond); MS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 456 [M⁺] (40.7), 441 (84.7), 425 (57.6), 423 (47.5), 407 (42.0), 313 (88.9), 274 (11.5), 259 (15.0), 247 (12.7), 229 (13.5), 215 (16.9), 203 (11.9), 189 (17.8), 187 (20.3), 175 (31.4), 173 (33.0), 161 (32.0), 159 (37.3), 135 (44.9), 133 (41.5), 123 (40.7), 121 (51.7), 119 (50.8), 106 (61), 103 (54.2), 100 (47.5), 88 (78.8), 79 (61.0) and 69 (100). Acetylation of **2a** with Ac₂O and pyridine in the usual manner gave **2b**, crystallized from MeOH-CHCl₃, m.p. 178–180 °C (Found : C, 81.89; H, 11.67. C₃₄H₅₈O₂ requires : C, 81.85; H, 11.73%); IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1243 and 1731 (OAc), 1647, 1373, 2937 and 892 (trisubstituted double bond); ¹H NMR : δ 0.65, 0.74, 0.86, 0.89 and 1.07 (each 3H, s, 5 × -C-CH₃), 0.84 (6H, s, 2 × -C-CH₃), 0.79 (6H, d, *J* 6.68 Hz, -CH(CH₃)₂) and 0.87 (3H, d, *J* 6.36 Hz, >CH-CH₃), 2.05 (3H, s, OAc), 4.48 (1H, dd, *J*₁ 11.64 Hz and *J*₂ 4.34 Hz, H-3) and 5.23 (1H, ill-res. m, H-11); MS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 498 [M⁺] (17.0), 483 (59.3), 468 (61.0), 457 (21.2), 442 (28.8), 424 (28.8), 408 (47.5), 398 (16.1), 393 (21.2), 355 (100), 303 (13.6), 289 (14.4), 288 (14.6), 255 (15.3), 241 (22.9), 229 (32.2), 215 (22.9), 175 (31.4), 173 (36.4), 161 (30.5), 159 (39.0), 147 (24.6), 143 (25.4), 123 (75.4), 121 (44.1), 119 (53.4), 91 (40.7), 88 (54.2), 83 (46.6), 74 (78.8), 72 (83.1), 61 (50.8), 59 (51.7), 52 (50.8) and 51 (62.7).

Reduction of acervatone (2c) to acervatol (2a) with NaBH₄ :

To a solution of 0.125 g of acervatone (**2c**) in MeOH (35 ml) was added 0.25 g of NaBH₄ in small portions with stirring in the cold (0–5 °C). The mixture was then

kept at room temperature with stirring for 30 min and thereafter heated under reflux for 1 h. MeOH was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was treated with H₂O (25 ml), acidified with dilute HCl in the cold and extracted with Et₂O, washed with H₂O, dried and the solvent removed. The residue was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (30 : 1) eluate gave acervatol (**2a**) (0.122 g).

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References

- 1 P L Majumder, M Roychowdhury and S Chakraborty, *Phytochemistry*, 1998, **49**, 2375, P L Majumder, S Pal and S Majumder, *Phytochemistry*, 1999, **50**, 891. P L Majumder, S Guha and S Sen, *Phytochemistry*, 1999, **52**, 1365. P L Majumder, S Sen and S Banerjee, *Tetrahedron*, 1999, **55**, 6691, P L Majumder, S Sen and S Majumder, *Phytochemistry*, 2001, **58**, 581
- 2 P L Majumder, S Lahiri and S Pal, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1994, **71**, 645, P L Majumder, S Lahiri and N Mukhoti, *Phytochemistry*, 1995, **40**, 271
- 3 P L Majumder and A Pal, *Phytochemistry*, 1985, **24**, 2120, P L Majumder, A Pal and S Lahiri, *Indian J Chem Sect B*, 1987, **26**, 297, P L Majumder and S Ghosal, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1991, **68**, 88
- 4 P L Majumder, S Majumder and S Sen, *Phytochemistry*, 2003, **62**, 591
- 5 P L Majumder and J Chakraborty, *Tetrahedron*, 1985, **41**, 4973, P L Majumder and A Kar, *Phytochemistry*, 1989, **28**, 1487, P L Majumder and S Pal, *Phytochemistry*, 1990, **29**, 2717
- 6 P L Majumder and S Lahiri, *Indian J Chem, Sect B*, 1989, **28**, 771
- 7 P L Majumder, S Laha and N Datta, *Phytochemistry*, 1982, **21**, 478
- 8 P L Majumder and S Banerjee (née Bhattacharyya), *Phytochemistry*, 1990, **29**, 3052
- 9 F R Stermiz, T R Suess, C K Schaur, R A Bye (Jr) and O P Anderson, *J Nat Prod*, 1983, **46**, 417, S R Bhandari, A H Kapadi, P L Majumder, M Joardar and J N Shoolery, *Phytochemistry*, 1985, **24**, 801
- 10 P L Majumder and A Kar, *Phytochemistry*, 1987, **26**, 1127
- 11 F W Wehrli and T Nishida, "The Use of C-13 Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy in Natural Products Chemistry". In W Herz, H Grisebach, G W Kirby (eds), 'Progress in the Chemistry of Organic Natural Products' (Fortschritte der Chemie Organischer

- Naturstoffe), Springer-Verlag, Wien, 1979, 36, 1-229.
12. S. Boonyaratavej, R. B. Bates, S. Caldera and K. Suvannachut, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1990, 53, 209.
 13. W. H. Hui, K. Luk, H. R. Arther and S. N. Loo, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1971, 2826.
 14. M. F. Das, G. F. Da Silva, H. P. Fransisco, A. I. Gray, J. R. Lechat and P. G. Waterman, *Phytochemistry*, 1990, 29, 1629.
 15. J. H. Rechards and J. B. Hendrickson, "The Biosynthesis of Steroids, Terpenes and Acetogenins", Benjamin, 1964; R. B. Clayton, "Aspects of Terpenoids Chemistry and Biochemistry", ed. T. W. Goodwin, Academic Press, 1971; K. Nakanishi, T. Goto, S. Ito, S. Natori and S. Nozoe, "Natural Product Chemistry", Academic Press, New York, 1974, Vol. 1; K. Nakanishi, T. Goto, S. Ito, S. Natori and S. Nozoe, "Natural Product Chemistry", Kodansia, Tokyo, 1983, Vol. 3; D. R. Dalton, "Studies in Organic Chemistry", ed. P. G. Gassman, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1979, Vol. 7.